

Input from

for Fertilisers Europe

About P2GreenN

P2GreenN's ambition is to foster the paradigm shift in our current linearly organised urban blue infrastructure and agricultural nutrient management towards circular clean tech value chains that reduce N and P emissions. P2GreenN aims to develop innovative circular nutrient management systems that

- use wastewater and human urine and faeces from urban areas as a valuable resource,
- recycling N and P via four innovative clean technologies in three pilot regions into bio-based fertilisers,
- which are used for food production in agriculture across Europe, reducing dependencies on current mineral fertilisers.

P2GreenN will deliver sustainable and safe bio-based fertilisers that are produced in the EU with reduced environmental impact, recovering N and P from human excreta and wastewater.

Funded by
the European Union

Just like manure from livestock is used as a fertiliser, P2GreenN is repurposing excreta from humans and wastewater for comparable yield performance.

P2GreenN fertilisers contribute to making the European agri-food system more resilient.

Investing in P2GreenN technologies will help to contribute to the EU zero pollution strategy.

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Policy Brief

